

Gaussian Process Regression for extending wave in situ measurements: An experimental campaign

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Gaussian Process Regression for extending wave in situ measurements: An experimental campaign.

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ABSTRACT

Wave energy is recognized as one of the most promising sources of clean and abundant energy. Nonetheless, up to today this technology is still not commercially viable, due to a number of reasons, like the harshness of the sea environment, the expenses needed for the deployment and maintenance of devices in open ocean and the lack of information regarding wave parameters worldwide. Indeed, a proper characterization of the resource in a site is of quintessential importance for assessing the productivity of the site and dimensioning the supporting system of a device. This work wants to address the problem of the lack of data by resorting to spatial prediction techniques, using data gathered through an experimental campaign conducted at the wave basin facility available at the Ocean and Coastal Engineering Laboratory in Aalborg University. During this campaign two months of real data from a real in situ measuring device were replicated in the basin. In the middle of the basin, underwater, some concrete blocks were deployed in order to replicate a sudden shift in the bathymetry, which should act as a disturbance to the wave propagation and arise nonlinear phenomena. 19 wave gauges were present and recorded the wave elevation for the whole time. Then a scenario where only a part of the measuring devices were working was replicated by considering only the data from a subsample of wave gauges and inferring the parameters in the locations of the other devices from them, through a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) algorithm. The proposed algorithm was able to interpolate the parameters at the other locations, at the expense of a relatively low error, indicating that this set up could be used to increase the spatial coverage of the wave measuring buoys deployed worldwide or to provide an estimate of the parameters at a buoy that is not working at the time, like for maintenance operations.

KEY WORDS: Wave energy, Gaussian Process Regression, In situ measurements, Resource assessment, Spatial gap-filling

INTRODUCTION

Wave energy is emerging as a highly promising energy source Terroero González et al. (2021), expected to be instrumental in future energy production. It is anticipated to be a significant factor in the transition away from fossil fuels von Schuckmann et al. (2020). The appeal of wave energy lies in its advantages, such as its high predictability and availability Mackay et al. (2010), distinguishing it from other renewable resources like solar or wind. This technology should play a key role in future years in helping moving away from fossil fuels, as also the Communication from the European Commission of November 2020 invests on it EU (2020), setting the ambitious goals of installed capacity of at least 1 GW of ocean (wave and tidal) energy by 2030, and 40 GW, by 2050. Despite its potential, as of now, wave energy technologies have not achieved commercial viability, primarily due to their prohibitively high Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE) Giglio et al. (2023), Astariz and Iglesias (2015). This elevated LCoE stems from several factors. Firstly, there is no universally optimal device design suitable for all operational scenarios, creating a significant challenge Giorcelli et al. (2022), Trueworthy and DuPont (2020). Additionally, there is no effective control systems for all these devices in all of their working conditions Ringwood et al. (2023). There are also the maintenance and operation costs that are substantial Centeno-Telleria et al. (2022), as these activities must be carried out in oceanic environments, which significantly escalates expenses and damages rapidly the devices deployed. Moreover, there is a scarcity of comprehensive global data on wave parameters Yaakob et al. (2016), which hinders the development and optimization of these technologies, specially regarding the spatial distribution of the wave parameters, which are quintessential for a proper location assessment Konuk et al. (2023), not only for wave energy production, but also for offshore wind energy production Faraggiana et al. (2022). Also using computer-aided simulation is not perfectly feasible for simulating the ocean environment: these tools can be employed for studying the spatial variability of the waves and can also give accurate results Ashton

et al. (2014), Zhou et al. (2015), but, since the dynamics regulating the ocean are given by the Navier-Stokes equations, which are highly nonlinear and notoriously difficult to solve, simulating even brief periods accurately typically demands considerable computational resources Griffies (2000), making it an hardly viable option. In addition to that, post-processing operations, like bias correction techniques, are often needed *ad hoc* for the results of those numerical simulation to be accurate Penalba et al. (2023). To address these issues, further research and innovation are needed to make wave energy a more economically feasible and reliable energy source. This study aims to tackle one of the key challenges in wave energy development: the scarcity of essential wave parameters data, which is crucial for selecting the most optimal locations for deploying wave energy converters (WECs) Yavor et al. (2021). Typically, wave energy parameters are measured using buoys equipped with measuring devices McLeod and Ringwood (2022). However, these devices, much like the deployed WECs themselves, require regular maintenance. They are prone to becoming non-operative for extended periods due to the harsh marine environment's toll on the equipment. Addressing this issue is vital for improving the feasibility and efficiency of wave energy projects, as reliable data on wave parameters is fundamental for strategic deployment and optimization of wave energy technologies.

This paper proposes a solution to the challenge of maintaining continuous wave parameter data collection in situations where some measuring devices become inoperative. We simulate a real-world scenario in a specific area where several measuring devices are deployed, but only a subset remains operational. In this context, we employ Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) to reconstruct wave parameters at the non-operative buoys using data from the correctly working devices. This approach was tested in a carefully designed experimental campaign to gather the necessary data.

The structure of this paper is organized as follows. Firstly, a comprehensive description of the experimental setup, including the methods for data collection and processing is provided. Then, an explanation of the adaptation and implementation of GPR for this particular application is given. After that, the presentation and discussion of the results obtained from the experiment is provided. Finally, a compilation of conclusions drawn from these results, providing insights into the effectiveness and potential applications of this approach in wave energy parameter measurement, is presented.

EXPERIMENT SETUP

The experimental phase of this study was carried out in the wave basin at the Ocean and Coastal Engineering Laboratory of Aalborg University. This facility boasts a wave basin measuring 19.3 meters in length, 14.6 meters in width, and 1.5 meters in depth, with an active testing area of 13 meters by 8 meters. The basin is equipped with an advanced segmented wavemaker system. This system features 30 independent wave paddles, each capable of precise control, and includes active absorption technology.

For the purpose of the experiments, the basin's floor was modified by adding concrete blocks to mimic sudden changes in the bathymetry, as it is well known that a changing bathymetry is a source of nonlinearities for the wave propagation Madsen et al. (2006). Indeed, the literature indicates that sudden changes in bathymetry can heighten the risk of initiating nonlinear phenom-

ena such as wave slamming Paulsen et al. (2019). Additionally, a set of 19 wave gauges was deployed to record wave heights, replicating the function of in-situ measurement instruments. The generated waves in the tank were manipulated to slowly vary their spectrum, mirroring actual wave data and spectral parameters obtained from actual measurements of the DanWEC site Brodersen et al. (2013). This setup provided a controlled environment to accurately simulate real-world ocean conditions for this study.

In this research, we replicated two months' worth of oceanic conditions observed at the DanWEC site in the wave basin, using a scale factor of 1:200. 204 different sea states were launched one after the other in this way, each one lasting for around 450s. The 19 wave gauges were installed around the strategically placed concrete blocks within the basin and they played a crucial role in providing both training and validation datasets for the models being tested in this study. The wave gauges recorded the time series of the wave elevation in the points where they were deployed. From this time series it was possible to derive the frequency spectrum to calculate the wave parameter of interest H_s and T_e , by using the spectral moments.

$$H_s = \sqrt{4m_0} \quad (1)$$

$$T_e = \frac{m_{-1}}{m_0} \quad (2)$$

An image illustrating the wave gauges and the concrete blocks setup is presented in Figure 1 of the paper, while a plant showing the spatial distribution of the wave gauges is presented in Figure 2. From Figure 2, it is possible to notice the presence

Fig.1 Disposition of the wave gauges and of the concrete blocks in the basin.

of a wave gauge particularly far away from the others, in position (10.334, 4.2) [m], that acts as an undisturbed measurement recording the wave parameters away from the influence of the nonlinearities generated by the concrete blocks. For a more detailed description of the used instrumentation and of the experimental environment, the reader can refer to Faedo et al. (2023).

In Figure 3 and Figure 4 it is possible to see an example of the measured parameters H_s and T_e respectively along with their location in the basin.

SPATIAL REGRESSION ALGORITHM

In this work, a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) has been used for performing the spatial regression of the parameters measured

Fig. 2 Spatial distribution of the wave gauges in the active area of the basin.

Fig. 3 H_s measured values.

Fig. 4 T_e measured values.

by the wave gauges.

GPRs have been chosen for this work since they seem suited for this kind of interpolation due to a number of reasons, like their ability to provide an estimate of the uncertainty of the prediction, which can be useful when moving towards real applications Neal (2000). Additionally, GPRs are suited to work with low quantity of data that can even be sparse in space Rasmussen (2004), as

it actually is in our experimental setup. Furthermore, GPRs are abstract and general enough to be able to describe almost all phenomena but they also have tunable hyperparameters than can be tailored for the specific application Seeger (2004).

GPRs expand upon and generalizes traditional Kriging techniques, extending their application beyond geostatistics Ebden (2015), Christianson et al. (2022). A Gaussian Process (GP) is theoretically defined as a collection of random variables, where any finite subset of those variables follows a multivariate normal distribution Rasmussen and Williams (2006). In this context, the parameter of interest (*i.e.* T_e and H_s in this application) is viewed as outcomes of a stochastic process, which is characterized by two key functions: a mean function denoted as $m(x)$ and a covariance or kernel function, represented as $k(x, x')$. Calling the generic input point $x \in R^d$ (*i.e.*, in this study, length and width positions in the tank), where d is the dimension of our input space (in our case $d = 2$), N as the number of training points and T as the number of testing points, let us define several key elements:

1. $X \in R^{d \times N}$, this is the matrix that contains all the training input points. In our spatial regression context, these would be the coordinates of the locations where the measurements of the wave parameters were taken.
2. $f \in R^N$, these are the training output values, which represent the actual measurements observed at the training points.
3. $X^* \in R^{d \times T}$, this refers to the testing input points, essentially the other points in the input space where we aim to predict or estimate the output (in our case this points would be the positions of all the other wave gauges not used in the training set).
4. $f^* \in R^T$ this is the estimate of the output at the testing points.

Given these definitions, considering a constant mean function equal to 0, the estimate f^* at the testing points is represented as a normal distribution. The mean of this distribution is calculated as $K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}f$ while its variance is given by $K(X^*, X^*) - K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}K(X, X^*)$

$$f^* | f, X, X^* \sim \mathcal{N} \left(K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}f, K(X^*, X^*) - K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}K(X, X^*) \right) \quad (3)$$

In the above formulation:

- $K(X, X) \in R^{N \times N}$ is the training-training covariance matrix computed evaluating the kernel function between all possible training-training pairs of points.
- $K(X^*, X) \in R^{T \times N}$ is the testing-training covariance matrix computed evaluating the kernel function between all possible testing-training pairs of points. Since kernel function must be symmetric $K^T(X^*, X) = K(X, X^*)$
- $K(X^*, X^*) \in R^{T \times T}$ is the testing-testing covariance matrix computed evaluating the kernel function between all possible testing-testing pairs of points.

The mean of the prediction $K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}f$ contains two important terms:

1. $K(X^*, X)$ the testing-training covariance matrix, also known as cross-variance matrix. This matrix represents how much the points where predictions are made (test points) are related to the training points. This term captures the influence that the observed data (training points) have on the predictions at new, unobserved locations (test points)
2. $K(X, X)^{-1}$ the inverse of the training-training covariance matrix or simply the covariance matrix of the training points. It is used to 'normalize' or adjust the influence of the training data on the prediction. By taking the inverse of the covariance matrix of the training points, it effectively removes redundant information and adjusts for the interdependence of the training data. This process ensures that the prediction is not overly influenced by the correlations in the training data, so that 2 points collocated (or at very small distance) are actually seen as just one point and not two distinct ones.

A common practical choice during the implementation is that of setting $T = 1$ and just estimating one testing point at a time, since considering the testing-testing covariance would only increase the computational effort required without improving the accuracy.

As can be seen from the equations, here the main part of the model design is performed by the choice of the kernel function $k(x, x')$. Indeed the kernel function is the key component of the algorithm that models the spatial auto-correlation of the considered stochastic process Chen (2021). Different kernel functions exist, each one describing a different spatial auto-correlation in a stochastic process. Some of the most used kernel functions are:

- The Squared Exponential (SE) kernel:

$$k_{SE}(x, x') = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2l^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

- The Linear Exponential (LE) kernel:

$$k_{LE}(x, x') = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|}{l}\right) \quad (5)$$

- The Matérn kernel:

$$k_{Mat}(x, x') = \frac{2^{1-\nu}}{\Gamma(\nu)} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\nu}\|x - x'\|}{l}\right)^\nu K_\nu\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\nu}\|x - x'\|}{l}\right) \quad (6)$$

Typical choices for the ν parameter are 1.5 and 2.5 Rasmussen and Williams (2006). $\Gamma(\nu)$ is the Gamma Function of ν and K_ν is the modified Bessel function of the second kind.

- The Rational Quadratic (RQ) kernel:

$$k_{RQ}(x, x') = \sigma^2 \left(1 + \frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\alpha l^2}\right)^{-\alpha} \quad (7)$$

Here, typical choices for the α parameter are 0.5 and 2 Rasmussen and Williams (2006).

The kernels presented above, as most common kernels, are stationary kernels, in the sense that they depend only on the distance $\|x - x'\|$ and not on the specific values of both x and x' . All

those kernel function have an amplitude set by σ which quantifies the amount of variance of the stochastic process that can be inferred by its spatial auto-correlation described by the kernel. These functions have also a characteristic length, l , which sets the range inside of which it is possible to make spatial inference. For comparison, Figure 5 reports together the above described kernels using an $l = 1$ and a $\sigma = 1$.

Fig. 5 Most commonly used kernel functions, with unitary amplitude and characteristic length

To account also for measurement noise and to increase the numerical stability of the algorithm, another term is added to the kernel function: $\sigma_{err}^2 \delta_{xx'}$, where σ_{err}^2 is the error measurement variance (that can be seen as the average difference of two collocated measurements), while $\delta_{xx'}$ is the Kronecker Delta of x and x' . Due to the presence of the Kronecker Delta, this error variance term is added to the kernel only when $x = x'$ (only on the diagonal of the kernel matrix). In our setup, σ_{err}^2 was set to 0.001 and 0.0001 for the T_e and H_s respectively, and it was added mainly for numerical stability since the measurements were pretty accurate.

In the considered experimental setup, there was a total of 204 time snapshots in which each wave gauge recorded H_s and T_e . Since between those temporal snapshots, the behaviour of the parameters changed significantly, each time snapshot has been considered alone (no temporal correlation is considered in this work). Also the variance of the parameters changed and for this reason the σ parameter was set as the empirical standard deviation of the parameter (seen from the selected training points). The number of training points changed between 3 and 14, in order to test scenarios with different levels of sparsity of the training points. The selection of the training points was performed randomly (excluding the undisturbed wave gauge) 50 times for each setup. In the end it was possible to obtain $204 \times 11 \times 50$ setups. Still it remains to be set the l parameter of the reconstruction. Different values for this parameter have been tested starting from the average distance between the wave gauges $l = d_{avg} = \frac{1}{\binom{N}{2}} \sum_x \sum_{x' \neq x} \|x - x'\| = 1.2755$ [m], where N is the number of considered points, and then trying $d_{avg}/2 = 0.6377$ [m], $d_{avg}/4 = 0.3189$ [m], $d_{avg}/8 = 0.1596$ [m] and $d_{avg}/16 = 0.0797$ [m]. The parameter measured by the undisturbed wave gauge has been used as an estimate of the mean of the process, which was then subtracted from the measurements

at the training points, and only the errors with respect to this mean were actually interpolated at the testing points.

For each of these reconstructions the Mean Absolute Relative Error (MARE) was computed.

$$\text{MARE} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i} \quad (8)$$

where T is the number of considered testing points (equal to 18 minus the number of training points), y_i is the real value of the estimated parameter at the i^{th} testing point and \hat{y}_i is the estimate of the parameter at the i^{th} testing point. All the reconstructions were repeated considering 6 different kernels:

1. SE kernel;
2. LE kernel;
3. Matérn 3/2 kernel;
4. Matérn 5/2 kernel;
5. RQ 0.5 kernel;
6. RQ 2 kernel.

OBTAINED RESULTS

The results of the reconstruction are summed up by Figure 6 which describes the average MARE, with respect to all the time instants and all the random permutations of the training points, for all the kernels, all the characteristic lengths and all the possible different number of training points for both T_e and H_s .

Those results are summarized by Table 1 and Table 2 that contain the average MARE with respect to all the possible number of training points, for different characteristic lengths and kernels used in the reconstruction for both H_s and T_e .

Table 1 Average MARE for H_s , for different kernels and characteristic lengths

H_s	SE	LE	Matérn 3/2	Matérn 5/2	RQ 0.5	RQ 2
d_{avg}	0.15313	0.11552	0.13197	0.14248	0.14131	0.14893
$d_{avg}/2$	0.146	0.11255	0.11875	0.1257	0.12572	0.13603
$d_{avg}/4$	0.11717	0.11236	0.11094	0.1116	0.11164	0.11388
$d_{avg}/8$	0.1134	0.11676	0.11499	0.1144	0.10936	0.11157
$d_{avg}/16$	0.12405	0.12291	0.12329	0.12349	0.11259	0.12062

Table 2 Average MARE for T_e , for different kernels and characteristic lengths

T_e	SE	LE	Matérn 3/2	Matérn 5/2	RQ 0.5	RQ 2
d_{avg}	0.038696	0.02598	0.029925	0.033582	0.034155	0.036625
$d_{avg}/2$	0.035172	0.025256	0.026795	0.028807	0.029481	0.032678
$d_{avg}/4$	0.028051	0.02503	0.025011	0.02535	0.025541	0.026235
$d_{avg}/8$	0.025646	0.026088	0.025816	0.025738	0.024781	0.025121
$d_{avg}/16$	0.027634	0.027404	0.027487	0.027526	0.025331	0.026954

For both T_e and H_s , using the entire d_{avg} as the characteristic length of the reconstruction gave poor performances and, with

this setup, the kernel that performed the better was the LE kernel, which is the kernel that gives the less amount of spatial correlation with fixed parameters (as can be seen Figure 5, where the LE kernel is the one with the lowest area under the curve). This fact alone should hint to the fact that better results could be obtained by using a lower characteristic length.

Indeed reducing the characteristic length gave better results for both parameters and for all kernels: as can be seen from Figure 6 and from 1-2 tables, the best performances are obtained for both T_e and H_s when using an RQ 0.5 kernel with a characteristic length of $d_{avg}/8$, with a MARE of 0.10936 and 0.024781 for H_s and T_e respectively.

Reducing even further the characteristic length starts worsening the results, as can be seen from the higher MARE for the $d_{avg}/16$ setup, when compared to the $d_{avg}/4$ and $d_{avg}/8$ setups. Another thing that can be seen from the results, is that the errors for H_s are almost one order of magnitude higher compared with the errors of T_e . This was already found in Gambarelli et al. (2023) and can be attributed to the fact that the Coefficient of Variance (CoV), equal to the mean of a variable divided by its standard deviation, is higher for H_s and lower for T_e , indicating that T_e has small perturbations of its values with respect to its mean, making it easier for T_e to achieve better metric performances.

$$\text{CoV}_x = \frac{\sigma_x}{\mu_x} \quad (9)$$

CONCLUSION

This preliminary work is a first attempt at trying to estimate wave parameter in a location using the measurements of nearby buoys, since this situation tends to happen often in practical applications (*e.g.* when a measuring device gets damaged and can not work until maintenance is effected). GPRs have been investigated for solving this problem and indeed they seemed to be effective in providing an accurate estimate of the wave parameters. From the results it is possible to draw several conclusions:

- Since the variance of the process generating the wave parameters changes time by time, the amplitude of the kernel addressing the spatial auto-correlation can be set instant-by-instant using the standard deviation empirically derived from the training points used in the considered snapshot.
- The characteristic length that seems to better capture the process variability between the considered ones results to be $d_{avg}/8$ for both T_e and H_s . This suggests that the length scale $d_{avg}/8$ captures the dominant features and patterns in the data. Anyway it is important to point out that this result may also be favored by the spatial disposition of our wave gauges. Indeed by changing the positions of the measuring devices (moving them further away or more closer to each other) the most optimal characteristic length for the reconstruction can change towards lower scale or higher scale features.
- Also the optimal kernel results to be the same for both T_e and H_s , suggesting that the RQ 0.5 kernel is the one that better describes the spatial auto-correlation of the process. The observation that the RQ 0.5 kernel yields the highest correlation at greater distances, among the kernels evaluated, suggests that the process under consideration exhibits a significant degree of non-locality. This implies

Fig. 6 Obtained average MARE for different kernels, characteristic lengths and number of training points

that the influence of any given point in the process extends over a wider range, rather than being predominantly local.

In conclusion, it is pertinent to note that while significant improvements in our model were achieved with the l parameter set at $d_{avg}/8$, there is a strong likelihood that further refinement of the l parameter in proximity to this value could yield even more optimal results. A more granular examination of the l parameter around $d_{avg}/8$ might uncover finer nuances in the data, potentially enhancing the model's accuracy and effectiveness. A final remark should be made on σ_{err}^2 : this parameter did not play a key role in this setup mainly because of the high accuracy that it is possible to have only in a laboratory. Anyway when going towards real world applications, this parameter becomes really important and a proper tuning of it can help obtaining accurate results. Moreover by giving different values of it to different input points it is also possible to obtain a multi-fidelity reconstruction, by considering some measuring devices more accurate than others and so considering them more trust-worthy Forrester et al. (2007), Gioia et al. (2022).

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